

D7.3 Communication strategy and plan V2

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5g-iana.eu

Authors

Authors in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	Email
Andrea Suárez	VICOM	asuarez@vicomtech.org
Edoardo Bonetto	LINKS	edoardo.bonetto@linksfoundation.com
Eirini Liotou	ICCS	eirini.liotou@iccs.gr

Control sheet

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
5G-IANA	5G for Intelligent automotive Network Applications
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility
DML	Distributed Machine Learning
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
nApp	Network Application
OBU	On-Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
R&I	Research and Innovation
RSU	Road-Side Unit
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
VNF	Virtualised Network Function
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current document presents the progress made on 5G-IANA communication and liaison¹ tasks during the first 21 months of the project. It constitutes an updated version of [D7.2-Communication strategy and plan](#), submitted in M9.

5G-IANA's communication strategy is fully aligned with the third-party engagement plan that the project has defined for increasing the participation of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to the activities of the project. This deliverable, D7.3, presents the updates adopted by the 5G-IANA communication strategy in terms of objectives, target audiences, key messages, and updated KPIs, as well as the new communication roadmap in line with this engagement plan. The document also presents the specific communication plan defined for the two Open Call periods that will take place during the course of the project.

The deliverable also covers the aspects related to liaison activities and international cooperation and provides a summary of the activities implemented until M21 together with the planned activities for the second half of the project.

The deliverable consists of the following sections:

- Chapter 1 consists of an introduction to the 5G-IANA project's concept and approach, to the purpose of the deliverable and intended audience.
- Chapter 2 presents the update of the communication strategy.
- Chapter 3 describes the liaison activities and planning.
- Chapter 4 is the conclusion.

¹ 5G-IANA dissemination strategy and activities are presented in deliverable D7.6-Dissemination Plan.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 5G-IANA concept and approach

5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third-party experimenters, i.e., SMEs in the Automotive vertical sector will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. The provided Automotive Open Experimentation Platform (AOEP) is a set of hardware and software resources that provides the computational and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced nApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector, for simplifying the design and onboarding of new nApps. 5G-IANA exposes to experimenters secured and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA targets different virtualization technologies integrating different Management and Orchestration (MANO) frameworks for enabling the deployment of end-to-end network services across different segments (vehicles, road infrastructure, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud resources). 5G-IANA nApp toolkit is linked with an Automotive Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) Repository including an extensive portfolio of ready-to-use and openly accessible Automotive-related VNFs and nApp templates, that are available for SMEs to use and develop new applications. Finally, 5G-IANA develops a Distributed Machine Learning (DML) framework, that provides functionalities for simplified management and orchestration of collections of Machine Learning (ML) service components and thus, allows ML-based applications to penetrate the Automotive world, due to its inherent privacy-preserving nature. 5G-IANA will be demonstrated through seven Automotive-related use cases in two 5G Stand Alone (SA) testbeds. Moving beyond technological challenges, and exploiting input from the demonstration activities, 5G-IANA will identify and validate market conditions for innovative, yet sustainable business models for the AOEP platform, supporting a long-term roadmap towards the pan-European deployment of 5G as a key advanced Automotive services enabler.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable belongs to the set of WP7 deliverables, and it is directly linked to Task 7.1 on Communication strategy and tools and T7.3 on Liaison activities and international cooperation. The document provides a detailed summary of the actions and activities

that have been applied by the 5G-IANA project up to M21 and the future plans and activities expected for the second half of the project.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of this document is “public” (PU) and is primarily aimed at the consortium members and the European Commission. However, any interested actor is able to download it and read it.

2. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The main goal of the 5G-IANA communication strategy is to create and spread awareness about the project and its results to the broadest possible target audiences, providing adequate information to them. In 5G-IANA, the engagement of third parties, i.e., SMEs and start-ups, with the 5G-IANA platform is crucial for achieving a high impact. In order to increase the participation of third parties to the activities of the project, a specific “third party engagement workplan” was defined by the project (Figure 1 – bottom part). This plan is comprised of different phases that align with the technical work that is being implemented through the technical WPs of the project (Figure 1 – top part).

Figure 1, Timeline of the engagement plan in alignment with the project workplan

The project’s communication strategy is fully aligned with this engagement plan through the third party workplan. Thus, the communication strategy, objectives, target audiences, key messages, and the roadmap have been adapted in line with this plan for the second part of the project.

2.1. Objectives

5G-IANA communication objectives have been revisited as follows:

- Identify target audiences, with a special focus on SMEs/start-ups working on the automotive vertical, and define tailored key messages to address to them, developing adapted high-quality communication materials and tools to ensure the achievement of the project’s objectives.

- Build awareness of the project's mission, activities, and results, informing our target audiences about the advantages of the project and engaging them through tailored communication activities and channels. Especially this objective has been revisited with the main focus to communicate the capabilities and offerings of the 5G-IANA platform, so as to attract and engage potential third party experimenters.
- In sequence, reach out to third parties (i.e., experimenters outside of the consortium) in a more personalised way, to engage them in onboarding and validating their Application Functions/Network Functions (AFs/NFs)/nApps on the 5G-IANA Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP).
- Establish and maintain cooperation with relevant 5G-PPP projects and other initiatives and bodies in the automotive sector.

2.2. Target audiences

In line with the project's third party workplan, target audiences identified for 5G-IANA's communication activities have been revisited as follows:

- **SME profiles (targeted):** Service Creators: all types of service creation entities such as software developers; Service Providers: who are responsible for providing a service to end users (for example Intelligent Driving, HD maps, etc.); Application and Network Functions Developers: who develop Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), i.e., Application Functions (AFs) and/or Network Functions (NFs) that can be used as building blocks for creating nApps; Application and Network Functions Providers: who are responsible for providing AFs and NFs to be on-boarded through the functionalities provided by the 5G-IANA platform; Network Application Developers: who are responsible for the development of Network Applications (nApps); Network Application Providers: who provide the nApps either to end users or service creators/providers. The goal for reaching out to this specific audience category is to attract SMEs to use the provided platform for experimentation during or even after the project's lifetime.
- **ICT Industry (in general):** Infrastructure Providers who provide different types of resources such as Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), Cloud Providers and Road Infrastructure Operators; Vendors who provide either HW or SW to all other actors; Vehicle manufacturers (OEMs) who provide the vehicles; Service Developers who include all types of service creators and research centres. The goal for reaching out to this specific audience category is for potential business exploitation of the 5G-IANA platform and its key elements.

- **Scientific and research community:** Academic and Research Centres; Operators of test sites and living labs to integrate piloted technologies for future applications, etc. The goal for reaching out to this specific audience category is cross-fertilization and transfer of results to follow-up initiatives.
- **5G-PPP projects and initiatives** and bodies active in the automotive vertical.
- **Institutions:** Policy and decision makers at European and national level; Standardisation bodies; National or regional funding bodies, etc. The goal for reaching out to this specific audience category is for implementation and follow-up/take-up aspects.
- **General Public:** Sector organisations representing industry end users; user groups impacted by developed technologies; end-user associations, etc. The goal for reaching out to this specific audience category is for acceptance, usability and impact assessment as well as take-up aspects.

2.3. Key messages

A set of key messages has been developed for each of the target audiences, considering their specific needs and typical characteristics.

➤ **SME profiles (targeted):**

5G-IANA is a project that is mainly addressed to SMEs and start-ups in the automotive vertical. Our goal is to provide an experimentation infrastructure on top of which third party experimenters will be able to test their applications. In more detail, given their participation in the project's Open Calls, the interested stakeholders may:

- Gain access to a “canvas” to develop new functions and services in the automotive 5G landscape.
- Test and validate their existing or new services in real-time using 5G connectivity.
- Gain access to real-life 5G resources (vehicles, OBUs, RSUs, EDGE/MEC Server(s)).
- Get continuous mentorship and support from network and automotive experts.
- Explore/Build new business models within the 5G ecosystem.
- Gain visibility towards the EU, the 5G community and the automotive community.

These are the key messages that 5G-IANA is promoting to SMEs through the Open Call (Section 2.6.1).

➤ **ICT Industry (in general):**

5G-IANA will potentially inform the various stakeholders in the ICT industry about the potential benefits from the exploitation of the AOEP platform, the developed technologies, as well as of the various independent AFs/NFs or even nApps that the project will develop. The opportunity that some of these AFs/NFs could be onboarded for instance on the OBUs, RSUs or MEC of respective manufacturers/providers/vendors will be thoroughly communicated. The examples and demos of the project's use cases will also be used to show how 5G adds value to the automotive vertical for various scenarios related to safety, infotainment, etc. With regards to vehicle OEMs and relative SW/HW providers in the automotive industry, 5G-IANA aims:

- To inform them about the extension of MANO to support on-vehicle deployment and the potentials of a distributed ML framework in an automotive related environment.
- To demonstrate the feasibility and added value that network status monitoring and Predictive Quality of Service (QoS) can bring to various automotive applications.
- To showcase the potential to safeguard the safety of drivers but also to increase their (co-)driving experience, through the examples of the project's use cases.
- To demonstrate how 5G brings value and added benefit both in technical terms but also enlarges their business potential.

➤ **Scientific and research community:**

5G-IANA aims to cooperate with the scientific and research community, with the following main objectives:

- To communicate research findings on 5G automotive-related services and nApps.
- To communicate research findings on the potentials of a distributed ML framework in an automotive-related environment.
- To communicate research findings on the developments and results of the demonstrated Use Cases.
- To contribute to Europe's activities to advance 5G technologies in the automotive sector.

➤ **5G-PPP projects and initiatives:**

The participation of 5G-IANA in the 5G-PPP Steering and Technology Board as well as in various Working Groups aims to promote the project's platform and nApps to relative projects working on similar concepts, with the ultimate goal to form liaisons that can lead

either a) to joint works such as White Papers that centrally highlight EU projects' contributions to the various vertical sectors or even b) to bilateral collaborations (especially with ICT-41 projects), to hopefully find a common way and ground towards interworking of nApps throughout the various developed platforms or at least commonly accepted exploitation schemes / market potential of them.

With respect to other institutions such as [5GAA](#), [ERTICO](#), etc. the goal is to promote the project's activities especially with regards the opportunities to engage SMEs for experimentation during the project's lifetime, or for exploitation even after the project's end.

➤ **Institutions:**

The interaction with institutions would be mainly in the direction of drawing conclusions on the potential impact of the 5G-IANA solution considering the benefits that it offers versus recapping on the factors potentially hampering its penetration (alternative/competitive solutions, infrastructure constraints, costs, standardisation time, legal issues, etc.). Indicative messages are as follows:

- 5G-IANA aims to accelerate 5G network deployments in Europe.
- 5G-IANA will share its results and outcomes, highlight the gaps and propose new, harmonized solutions.
- 5G-IANA will contribute to existing standards and identify new ones.

➤ **General public:**

The main message that will be transferred to this group has to do with promoting Europe's activities and funding efforts to advance 5G, having 5G-IANA as an example of an open platform that enables interested and relevant stakeholders to get into the 5G landscape, an opportunity that would otherwise not be available to them. Some of the messages communicated will be the following:

- 5G-IANA aims to accelerate the creation and commercialisation of 5G-based automotive Applications.
- 5G-IANA aims to increase road safety, improve road utilization, and augment the (co-)driving experience.
- 5G-IANA aims to sustain the promotion of Europe as leader in 5G technology.

2.4. Communication tools and channels

The communication tools and channels selected to ensure the 5G-IANA's information flow, to guarantee a wide and timely communication, to create awareness and to reach out to the targeted audience have been established during the first months of the project and reported on the initial versions of the communication deliverables ([D7.2](#) and [D7.4](#)). In line with the project's third party workplan, new channels have been created and some existing channels have been re-adapted as required. The full list of communication tools and channels is provided below briefly, while detailed information on each of these tools and channels is provided in the second version of the Communication tools ([D7.5](#)).

- **Brand Identity and logo:** to create a coherent, consistent, and highly recognisable image of the project that supports communication and dissemination activities.
- **Website:** as the main repository for the project's outputs and resources. The website has been updated during this period with the aim of improving the [level of technical information](#) and easing the access to the available resources and News. In parallel, a new section called "[Get Involved](#)" aiming to guide external experimenters on how they can engage in the open experimentation of the 5G-IANA platform has been released in February 2023, together with the release of the first Open Call of the project.
- **Social media accounts:** [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#) and [YouTube Channel](#).
- **Newsletter:** conceived to raise interest about the project's activity, advancements and upcoming and past events; its periodicity has been reduced from six to every four months.
- **Digital and printed communication materials:** first versions of the flyer (M08), the poster (M12), the brochure (M18), and the roll-up banner (M12) have been already published, and second versions, focused on the users of the project's outcome, are in progress at the time of writing this document. Additionally, digital flyers and social media banners have been specifically created to support 5G-IANA Open Call #1 promotional campaigns.
- **Press releases and conferences:** press releases are published by the consortium at key moments of the project, aiming to communicate important information to target audiences and announcing significant achievements and major upcoming events. They are prepared in English by the Communication Manager and distributed among the partners who are responsible for their adaptation to the local contexts. Press conferences will be organised during the demo events to ensure maximum stakeholder engagement.

- **Videos:** 5G-IANA will produce ten videos in total; three project-related videos and at least one short video per UC. The [first introductory video](#) of the project was created in M17.
- The **5G-IANA H2020 Project Zenodo Community**, created in M14 of the project, where outputs of the project are being made publicly available and under open access status.
- **Webinars**, and a Hackathon: specialised webinars, a Hackathon (planned around M35/M36) and training events will be organized to engage third party experimenters.

Table 1 identifies the relevant communication activities to the different target audiences:

Table 1, Target audiences and communication activities

Communication Activities	Target Groups					
	SMEs	ICT industry	Scientific and research community	5G-PPP projects and initiatives	Institutions	General public
Brand Identity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media	✓			✓		✓
Newsletter	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Digital and printed communication materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press releases	✓	✓		✓		✓
Press conferences	✓					✓
Videos	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Zenodo Community	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Webinars	✓	✓		✓		
Email campaigns	✓	✓		✓		
Presentations at relevant groups	✓	✓		✓		

Comms 5G-PPP channels	✓	✓		✓		
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2.5. Communication activities (roadmap)

A series of communication activities are being implemented throughout the project’s lifecycle. As previously highlighted, the engagement of third parties is crucial for achieving a high impact in 5G-IANA. Therefore, in line with the “third party workplan”, we differentiate two main type of communication activities:

- General communication activities: aiming to raise awareness of the project’s developments and challenges, promote activities and information of the project, and promote the final results of the project.
- Targeted third party engagement communication activities, aiming to involve external SMEs in the open experimentation of 5G-IANA platform.

Applying this approach, 5G-IANA communication activities and phases have been revisited as follows:

2.5.1. Initial phase

The initial objective of the communication activities was to create a coherent, consistent, and highly recognisable image of the project aiming to enable and to maintain the integrity of the project’s overall brand identity to ensure an efficient communication and dissemination of the project and its results. The [logo](#), the colour palette, the fonts, etc. that set the basis of the project’s brand and visual identity were designed in the first months of the project and compiled in the project’s Brand Book. Additionally, the project’s reference document on brand material and guidelines, [Deliverable D7.1 \(Brand Identity and guidelines\)](#), was issued in M06 providing the consortium clear guidelines on how to correctly use 5G-IANA’s brand and visual identity elements as well as project branded templates to ensure a coherent and efficient communication of the project and its results.

During the first months of the project, the aim of the communication activities was also to create awareness about the project and to generally inform target stakeholders about the project’s main objectives and expected outcomes and results. For this purpose, the project set up the main communication tools: the social media channels (M01) and the website (M06). These two main communication tools have helped to effectively raise

awareness of the project, its nature, and also to promote the first project’s activities and advancements. The communication and dissemination activities performed and promoted through these two channels have set the ground to start creating an active community of general audience and stakeholders. Together with the first [press release](#) of the project (M07), another key tool seeking to support the objective of informing target stakeholders about the project’s main objectives and expected outcomes and results was the release of the project’s first versions of the printed communication materials: the [flyer](#) (M08), followed by the [poster](#) (M12) and the [brochure](#) (M18). The [roll-up banner](#) was also designed in M12 to be used for internal meetings and external events.

Further actions targeting to connect the community of general audience and stakeholders with the project were the issue of the project’s first series of the [Newsletter](#) (M08), the setup of the [5G-IANA H2020 Project Zenodo Community](#) (M14) and the release of the [first introductory video](#) of the project (M18).

2.5.2. Development and validation phase

The second communication phase is fully aligned to the project’s third-party workplan (Figure 2).

Figure 2, Third party workplan timeline

The main objectives of this phase (“Promotion”) are the following: a) to attract and involve third party experimenters outside of the consortium to become aware of the 5G-IANA platform and its capabilities as well as to attract them to get involved in experimentation activities through the project’s Open Calls, and b) to promote the activities performed by the selected experimenters together with insightful results obtained during the pre-testing, validation, and report phases of the Open Calls.

Activities under this phase are being implemented in cross-collaboration with WP6 and already started in M16 with the preparation and coordination of the materials required to execute the promotion and communication of the Open Calls to effectively engage experimenters. These materials are being used to develop concrete communication tools and activities such as: a new dedicated website section aimed to inform and engage third

parties and advertise the project's Open Calls; preparing "template" email communications to internal and external stakeholders; creating specific digital promotional materials that support high-impact social media campaigns; producing updated versions of the printed communication materials focused on the users of the project's outcome; or organising dedicated webinars.

So as to widely transmit the 5G-IANA messages and developments to the target audiences and engage relevant stakeholders (third party experimenters in the form of SMEs mainly), a strong effort is being dedicated to promotional campaigns through social media, website news articles, press releases, email communications and promotional 5G-PPP Communication lists, supported by communication materials specifically developed for the occasion.

The 5G-IANA consortium will also leverage communication and dissemination tools to promote dedicated webinars (e.g., the 5G-IANA AOEP description, an Info Day, the presentation of the 5G testbeds, practical examples of nApps for the automotive sector, etc.), the Hackathon and training events.

Videos will be a powerful tool during this phase for the engagement of third parties as well as for the promotion of the activities and results already achieved. The second video of the project is planned around M30, in parallel with the promotion of the project's second Open Call and plans to provide a "how-to-experiment tutorial" to the selected SMEs and third party experimenters and a hands-on showcase of the platform capabilities, together with some practical nApp examples. At least one short video per use case will be also created.

To the maximum extent possible, the project will try to organise physical events leveraging potential internal or external events to promote the Open Call activities. Together with the Hackathon, at least two demo events have been planned where the use cases will be showcased.

Along with these activities delimited in the third party workplan, the Communication leader will keep addressing general communication activities by promoting all dissemination events and project activities through the available channels (website, social media, newsletters, etc.).

2.5.3. Final phase

The main objective of this phase will be the dissemination and promotion of the project's final results, demonstrating the value of the results to stakeholders from all the target groups via all communication and dissemination tools and activities established.

A Final Event will be organised where the 5G-IANA final findings and lessons learnt will be presented. An exceptional promotional campaign will take place for this event through all available communication channels. A press release will be issued prior to the event, while journalists will be also invited to the event for a media conference and to experience first-hand the project results through demos and interviews with consortium members. A final video will be created for the occasion and presented during the event. All materials created and/or obtained from this event (presentations, video, demos, discussions, etc.) will be disseminated through the project's website and social media and through a final edition of the Newsletter.

2.6. Next steps

As shown in Figure 2, the second half of the project will be dominated by the two Open Calls that the project is organising. For this reason, the project's Communication management has defined a specific plan for the promotion and communication of 5G-IANA Open Calls. The activities envisaged under this plan will be implemented in three phases:

- Phase 1: Announcement of the Open Call and preliminary communication | Cycle A (M19-M21), Cycle B (M29-M31)
- Phase 2: Main Open Call communication | Cycle A (M22-M24), Cycle B (M32-M34)
- Phase 3: Follow-up communication | Cycle A (M25-M30), Cycle B (M35-M40)

The project's Communication Leader will centralise and lead all the promotional activities defined under this specific plan, although the partners will be also engaged in supporting them from their own channels. To facilitate this, the Communication Management will release to the Consortium and the partners the "5G-IANA Open Call Communication Guidelines": a document summarising the steps, the timelines, and the resources available to execute the promotional campaigns at each stage with the ultimate target of reaching out to a broader audience to participate in 5G-IANA Open Calls and to disseminate the results to the broadest audience possible. This document will be regularly monitored, and updated versions will be issued at the beginning of each communication phase to provide the latest information and guidelines for the prompt and efficient communication of the

Open Calls. The first version of this document, describing the announcement phase of Open Call #1 and its preliminary communication, has been already issued. Figures 3 and 4 below present these communication phases and related documentation:

Figure 3, 5G-IANA Open Call (OC) #1 Communication timeline

Figure 4, 5G-IANA Open Call (OC) #2 Communication timeline

The main repository of information as well as the main communication tool during the Open Call periods will be the dedicated section “[Get Involved](#)” on the 5G-IANA website launched on M21 together the Open Call #1 (more details about this section are provided on D7.5 Communication tools V2). Specific materials like digital flyers used for announcements (launch, Info Day, application dates, results, etc.), social media banners for supporting promotional campaigns more efficiently, social media posts templates, email templates, press releases templates, etc. have been and will continue to be designed and issued during the course of the Open Calls. Furthermore, updated and new versions of the printed communication materials -focused on the users of the project’s

outcome- will be issued to support the engagement, and to increase the interest of third party experimenters.

2.6.1. 5G-IANA Open Call #1

5G-IANA Open Call #1 has been launched in February 2023 and will last until December 2023 as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5, 5G-IANA first Open Call timeline

In accordance with the three-phase communication plan, 5G-IANA Open Call #1 promotional activities will be implemented as follows:

Phase 1: Announcement of the OC#1 and preliminary communication (M19, M21):

The objective of this phase has been to approach the targeted SMEs ecosystem.

The main activity of this Phase is the official announcement of the Open Call in February 2023. This announcement has been done through a press release published on the website and promoted on social media. The partners will adapt it and promote it on their own channels and languages.

Additionally, several activities have been implemented in an earlier promotional campaign: an email campaign targeting potential interested SMEs identified by the Consortium was implemented (M19), the Open Call has been promoted through 5G-PPP channels since M20 (a [presentation at the 5GPPP SMEs Working Group](#) was addressed

and the Open Call has been [announced on the 5G-PPP website](#)), and an intense promotional [social media campaign](#) has been already initiated (M20). A final active email campaign will be addressed at the end of this phase officially inviting potential interested experimenters to take part in the Open Call (this invitation will include an invitation to the “Info Day” that the project will organise in M22 (14/3/2023)). This campaign will be implemented through an extensive use of internal and external communication channels and networks of all partners, liaison activities with ICT-41 projects, and other associations (5G-PPP/5G-IA and WGs, 5G-PPP Comms, etc.).

Phase 2: Main OC#1 communication (M22-M24):

The core activity of Phase 2 will be the intense promotion of the Open Call process for attracting SME applicants. This will be done through active website and social media campaigns, a dedicated Newsletter about the Open Call, targeted mailing lists (e.g., 5G-PPP “5G for CAM” and “SMEs” WG), and promotional 5G-PPP Comms (Newsletters and Newsflashes). Furthermore, a webinar campaign is foreseen during this phase focused on attracting the attention of experimenters:

- An “Info Day” planned for M22 where key technical members of the project will present the project, the 5G-IANA AOEP Release 1, the 5G-IANA offerings and nApps, as well as the logistics and administrative procedures for applying to the Open Call.
- A webinar with the official presentation of the 5G-IANA test sites at NOKIA and Telecom Slovenia, including information about the features of autonomous vehicles, OBUs and RSUs offered by 5G-IANA.

An intense promotional campaign will be specifically implemented for the promotion of these webinars through social media and a news article on the website. The recordings will be also uploaded on the web to be widely promoted on social media, within the 5G-PPP community and through the project partners’ networks.

Phase 3: Follow-up communication (M25-M30):

The main objective of this third phase will be to inform the public about the progress and achievements of the Open Calls (results and winners) following the selected experiments’ execution.

These announcements will be done through website and social media campaigns, Newsletters, and through promotional 5G-PPP Comms (Newsletters and Newsflashes) when possible. Announcement of the winners will be also done through a press release.

To the maximum extent possible, the project will make an effort to identify external events or conferences to announce the winners to ensure high visibility. Furthermore, the project will attempt to organise an internal event to announce the winners and already inform stakeholders about the period where the 2nd Open Call will open for interested SMEs.

During this phase, the project also foresees to organise another webinar: a user-guide "training" type of webinar, in the form of a how-to-experiment tutorial with hands-on showcasing of the procedure: i.e., demonstration of onboarding nApps and of the overall platform capabilities, together with practical examples of nApps for the automotive sector, based on the 5G-IANA Use Cases as exemplary scenarios. This webinar will be used to create the second video of the project (around M30) that will support the promotion of the second Open Call.

2.7. Monitoring and reporting of communication activities

The communication activities have been designed to have an impact on the target stakeholders and serve to advance the project's goals. Although it is difficult to assess the accurate impact of the project's communication activities, quantitative indicators present some measurable values to help the consortium evaluate the degree to which the targets of the communication plan are met. For this, 5G-IANA has defined a set of communication KPIs (Table 2) that will be regularly monitored.

2.7.1. Key Performance Indicators

The communication KPIs' target values have been updated to better reflect the project's capacity and extended duration. These are presented in Table 2 and indicate a target value for each communication tool, channel and activity per year.

Table 2, 5G-IANA KPIs for Communication tools/channels

Tool/Channel	Key Performance Indicator	Target value			
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
	Website: Total visits per month	100	160	300	>300

Communication tools	Twitter: 5G-IANA hashtags	80	160	250	300
	LinkedIn: Members of 5G-IANA Group (out of Consortium members)	65	130	260	>300
	Video: number produced	-	>2	>8	10
	Project brochure: number produced	1	Update	Update	3
	Technical leaflets: published and distributed	>100	>100	>100	300
	Press releases: number issued	1	2	6	9
	Newsletters: number of reads ²	50	100	150	200

* Y3 column includes all the produced results (performance) until the completion of 5G-IANA lifecycle, including the project's extension, i.e., M25 – M42.

2.7.2. Reporting and Monitoring Activities

2.7.2.1. Reporting

The 5G-IANA communication activities are reported in this deliverable, while the impact of the communication tools and channels until M21 are presented in the second version of the Communication tools (D7.5). This information will be also reported on the periodic reports.

2.7.2.2. Monitoring

- WP7 telcos: The WP7 telcos, held on a monthly basis, monitor the status and the progress of the entire WP. From a T7.1 level, the ongoing activities and related KPIs are presented to the partners as a way of monitoring the performance of the communication tools.
- GA meetings: GA meetings also take place monthly, chaired by the Project Coordinator. These congregate all the partners for the review of the overall status of the Project and all WP Leaders present the status of activities. It also serves as a great opportunity to synchronise the work being aligned by the different WPs through the third party engagement plan and plan future actions accordingly.

² This indicator is based on the number of subscribers plus the number of downloads of Newsletters in Zenodo.

3. Liaison Activities and International Cooperation

The liaison activities of the 5G-IANA project are being developed considering as main potential liaison partners those that share interests about the technical aspects that are tackled within 5G-IANA (i.e., 5G communications) or that are dealing with use cases in the automotive vertical and, more in general, in the CCAM field.

The first category of considered interlocutors is the European research projects. In particular, the ICT-41-2020 projects are the most promising as these projects are working on the same topics as 5G-IANA. Other considered interlocutors are 5G-PPP and SNS projects for the treated technical topics, and CCAM-related H2020 and HE projects for the similar vertical application domain. Further considered interlocutors are the CCAM- and 5G-related associations and organisations that can be potentially interested in establishing a cooperation with 5G-IANA.

The following liaison activities have been performed until the time of writing this deliverable:

- Contribution to the [5G-PPP brochure](#) in July 2021.
- Presentation of 5G-IANA to the 6G-IA 5G 4 CAM Working Group in December 2021.
- [5G-IANA at the ITS European Congress in Toulouse](#): 5G-IANA, 5G-MOBIX, and ICT4CART projects jointly participated in the Special Interest Session 20 “5G for ITS: comms, computational challenges and prospects” that took place on the 31st of May 2022.
- [A Special Session in collaboration with 5GASP project](#) “Netapps for Verticals” at the 2022 EuCNC & 6G Summit on 8th June 2022.
- Contribution to the white paper “[From 5G to 6G Vision - A Connected and Automated Mobility \(CAM\) perspective](#)” of the 6G-IA 5G 4 CAM Working Group in June 2022.
- [A Workshop Session “NetApp Platforms into Beyond 5G and 6G Networks”](#) at the Second IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom) on 5th September 2022, where representatives from other ICT-41 projects (5GASP, EVOLVED-5G, 5G-ERA, or Smart5Grid) participated.
- Contribution to the white paper “NetApp: Opening up 5G and beyond networks” of the 5G-PPP Software Networks Working Group in September 2022.
- A [Joint VITAL-5G & 5G-IANA presentation](#) during the 5G-PPP Steering Board and Technical Board meetings hosted by 5G-IANA Project Coordination on 5th and 6th

October 2022. During these meetings, 5G-IANA Project Coordination also organised and chaired a nApps devoted session with interesting cross-ICT-41 discussions.

Besides the reported activities, discussions are ongoing to identify further liaison actions with the other ICT-41-2020 projects such as 5G-ERA, VITAL-5G, 5GASP, and EVOLVED-5G. Further planning of activities is being performed with other projects. A summary of the current status is provided next.

A dissemination liaison activity is under discussion between 5GMETA and 5G-IANA. The objective is a Special Interest Session (SIS) proposal for the ITS European Congress 2023. Additional liaison activities, that are under discussion with 5GMETA, are two webinars. The first one is scheduled at the beginning of May 2023, and it is expected to provide an overview of the platform that each project is developing. This webinar aims to promote the 5GMETA Second Hackathon and the 5G-IANA Open Call. A second webinar is scheduled in the last quarter of 2023. This webinar will focus on the achievements of the two projects and on the future projects' activities. A joint technical activity is also being discussed. The target of this activity would be to create a nApp related to the 5GMETA project that would be inserted in the 5G-IANA nApp Catalogue. This nApp will implement the required operational steps that an OBU should perform to interact with the 5GMETA platform.

A liaison activity is foreseen with the [Hexa-X-ii](#) project on technological aspects. This activity will target a joint technical workshop in which common topics of interest will be discussed. At the moment, there are ongoing discussions for identifying the relevant topics. The timeframe for concretely defining this activity is expected for June 2023. The project started on January 2023 (i.e., one month before at the time of writing this deliverable), and it is currently in a too-early stage for defining concrete activities.

The focus of 5G-IANA on the automotive vertical makes it relevant to establish a connection with the HE project [PoDIUM](#) (PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM). The PoDIUM project will demonstrate several use cases using 5G communication and related features. The project has PoDIUM started (i.e., October 2022), and there is an agreement between 5G-IANA and PoDIUM to discuss liaison activities from April 2023 onwards as the PoDIUM project will progress with its development activities.

The 5G-IANA Partner Bylogix identified the Italian Association “Associazione Nazionale Filiera Industria Automobilistica (ANFIA)”, which is the national association of the automotive Industry Supply Chain, as an association relevant to the 5G-IANA project. This association represents a point of contact with institutions and public decision-makers in Italy. Cooperation with this association would give visibility to the results of the 5G-IANA project in a national industrial and policy context. Furthermore, Bylogix is involved in an internal working group that addresses the ADAS-related aspects and, more generally, the theme of connected vehicles. This working group can be particularly relevant as an interlocutor of a joint activity with 5G-IANA. A joint webinar, during which respective activities are presented, has been planned, and it will be a starting point to define possible further liaison activities.

Other liaison activities performed are those related to the participation to Working Groups (WGs) that are organised from the 6G-IA or from 5G-PPP Projects. 5G-IANA Partners are following the activities of these WGs and Subgroups: “Pre-Standardization” WG, “Trials” WG, “Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystem” Subgroup, “Member States Initiatives” Subgroup, “5G/Beyond 5G Architecture” WG, “5G for CAM” WG, “Software Networks” WG, “SME” WG, “Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation” WG, “Open Smart Networks and Services” WG. In the “5G for CAM”, 5G-IANA contributed to the white paper “From 5G to 6G Vision: A Connected and Automated Mobility perspective”.

4. CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents the activities implemented on communication and liaison tasks until M21 of the project and incorporates the updates adopted by these tasks in line with the third party engagement plan defined by the project.

The document collects the updates adopted by the 5G-IANA communication strategy in relation to the objectives, target audiences, key messages, and the new KPIs' target values adopted to better reflect the project's capacity and extended duration. It covers the new communication phases (roadmap) re-aligned to this engagement plan and that differentiates between the more general communication activities and the targeted third party engagement communication activities. The document briefly summarises the communication tools and channels adopted by the project to execute the communication activities (detailed information on these tools and channels and their performance is provided in D7.5 delivered together with this document in M21 of the project) and goes through the liaison activities already performed as well as the detailed planning for the second half of the project. Finally, the document presents the specific communication plan defined for the two Open Call periods that will take place during the course of the project.

The final impact achieved by the communication activities is expected to be reported at the end of the project under D7.8 - Report on the dissemination activities (M42)³. The final impact achieved by liaison activities will be reported in D7.9 - Report on international cooperation and liaison activities at the end of the project.

³ The project plans to report the communication activities and the impact achieved by the communication tools and channels at the end of the project together with the final dissemination activities' report.